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<https://www.ijmsbr.com/>

Impact Factor: 6.049

Influence of Work-Life Balance on Employee Satisfaction at Financial Institutions in the Amparo District

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Abstract

Work-life balance (WLB) enables employees to strike a healthy balance between their professional and personal/family lives. Because of the changing nature of the employment market, the notion of WLB has gained traction in industry and academics. When individuals are required to meet more job-related objectives, the job becomes more difficult. They must balance their professional lives with their personal lives. Employees in financial firms are likewise struggling to balance their professional and personal lives. At the same time, the job market has become more competitive. Furthermore, they have very little time to interact with society. As a result, the crucial question is whether they are content with their job. As a result, the study's issue statement was "How does work-life balance affect employee job satisfaction in financial institutions in the Ampara district?"

First, the researcher conducted a literature analysis and critically analyzed WLB and work satisfaction to further investigate the topic area. The researcher then sought to explore the primary three categories of WLB as individual factors, societal factors, and organizational aspects in terms of replies from financial institution employees. The study's sample size was 70 employees from financial institutions in the Ampara district. Data was gathered via questionnaires. The data was then examined using SPSS software, and hypotheses were tested using correlation and regression analysis. Since the hypotheses were accepted, the researcher concluded that all three components, individual, societal, and organizational, had an impact on the job satisfaction of employees in financial institutions in the Ampara district. As a result, employees who maintain a healthy work-life balance are more satisfied with their careers. Future scholars are encouraged to conduct additional research on the topic, using a larger sample size.

Key words: *Work Life Balance, Individual factors, Organizational factors, Social factors, Job satisfaction, financial institutions, Ampara district*

1.0.Introduction

Managing an individual employee is more challenging than ever due to the changing work environment. Having an unbalanced personal and professional life might result in a variety of problems. Employees who disperse their energy and efforts among the most important priorities live balanced lives. Work-life balance (WLB) is becoming a crucial component of managing staff in all positions. The majority of employees devote the majority of their waking hours to their jobs (Hochschild, 2012). Individual welfare is therefore the primary factor in maintaining a productive workforce (Lane, 2011). Numerous studies have demonstrated that low levels of job satisfaction can have detrimental effects on how employees carry out their responsibilities and their performance at work.

Taking into account Sri Lankan financial institutions, harmonizing work and personal obligations is crucial. Maintaining healthy work-life balance is crucial because the banking sector is a major provider of services to the economy (Dassanayaka & Ali 2013). Banking officers in Sri Lanka struggle to strike a balance between work and family life due to the rigid work schedules. The main causes of the problem include

working couples, problems with child care, and a lack of time for family care. Given the information, WLB is now essential. Organizations should reconsider their approach to employee well-being and quality of life if they want to increase employee happiness.

Individuals are finding it difficult to fulfill their obligations and responsibilities while working in today's highly dynamic culture. Work-life balance has therefore become crucial for both firms and employees. Businesses constantly strive to outperform their rivals and dominate their markets by improving both their productivity and profitability. Employees must put in a lot of effort and devote their entire lives to the organizations in order to reach this goal. As a result, there is less concern for employee lives and their personal lives are getting worse. Therefore, the majority of research studies have shown that organizations are implementing strategies to gain competitive advantage through innovative strategies, particularly put steps forward to manage work-life balance of employees. The majority of organizations are perceived that this may be a win-win situation for both employee and organization.

The financial industry in Sri Lanka has advanced significantly. Due to the intense competition among financial institutions, strategies have been developed to increase market share by luring in new clients and keeping hold of existing ones. They have extended their hours, added more items, created more branches, and implemented the most recent IT infrastructure in order to achieve this. As a result, their employees now work longer hours and have more difficult workloads, which puts them under a lot of work pressure. This has also contributed to a culture of poor work-life balance, which has led to a significant level of job dissatisfaction among their staff.

There is a severe lack of empirical data regarding how work-life balance affects employees' job satisfaction in financial institutions. Therefore, the research question under investigation in this study is, "Does work-life balance have an impact on employee job satisfaction in financial institutions in Ampara District?" The goal of this study is to determine the degree to which work-life balance, as well as individual, organizational, and social factors, affects employees' job satisfaction in financial institutions in Ampara, Sri Lanka.

2.0. Literature Review on Work Life Balance

WLB used to be viewed as an inter-role conflict that resulted from an imbalance between personal and professional life. (Kahn, 2013). Researchers have varied ideas about what the word WLB means. Carefully integrating work life with family and personal life is one definition for WLB (Greenhaus, 2012). Personal life and professional life are currently seen as two halves of the same coin. WLB is also defined as people who are equally engaged in and satisfied by their duties in both work and family life (Clark, 2015). In the interim, several academics have modified the definition of WLB; Clark defined it as the pleasure of one's personal and professional lives with the fewest possible inter-role conflicts (Clark, 2015). WLB is a crucial component of satisfied workers. The majority of businesses are aware of the value of WLB, which enables long-term staff retention, lowers employee stress levels, boosts job satisfaction, and improves family and work life balance (Susi, 2010).

Different authors offer several definitions of WLB, and the majority of them take into account the equality of the personal and professional lives. However, the majority of studies claimed that because of the pressures of both personal and professional life, employees would not be able to fully balance both. WLB is currently a subject that is hotly debated among authors and approached from many different viewpoints. Despite the fact that WLB addresses a lot of issues that are difficult to separate from work and life as if work were an inseparable component of life, (Lewis et al., 2017).

2.1. Theories On WLB

Since WLB is a broad term, numerous definitions have been provided by various authors. Key five models are provided by Zedeck, Mosier, and later O'Driscoll to interpret the connection between an employee's personal and professional lives. O'Driscoll, (2013) The first concept, also known as a segmentation model, claimed that work and family life are two separate realms with no connections between them. This model focuses more on theoretical aspects than on practical methods. The second model, known as the "spill over model," supports the first model by arguing that work and family life are two realms that can have an impact on one another either favorably or unfavorably. The third model is the compensation model, which contends

that job and family are two fields of life and that any demands or satisfactions that may be absent from one sphere of life can be obtained from the other. The fourth paradigm, the instrumental model, states that actions taken in one area may have a positive impact on another aspect. The fifth model, the conflict model, suggested that people experience high levels of demand in many areas of life and are forced to make difficult decisions, which may lead them to comprehend psychological conflicts and experience significant overload.

A new idea is introduced to WLB by Clark, who claims that every person's behaviors are unique and depend on physical, temporal, or psychological elements. According to the theory, people are migrating from their homes to their places of employment with a significant amount of work integration. Conflicts of this nature are as a result of the flexibility, rules, and boundaries between work and family life (Clark, 2015). According to Morris and Madsen's Resource Drain Theory and Enrichment Theory, the availability of scarce resources like time, money, energy, and attention leads to a decline in the amount of that resource in its original sphere as it is shared with other spheres. According to enrichment theory, practice from instrumental (skills, talents, values) or emotive (mood, satisfaction) sources can enhance the value of another sphere, or in other words, understanding in one sphere can elevate the standard of living in another. The aforementioned hypotheses were the subject of the majority of the research investigations in WLB, while individual studies may have varied in their clarification and content.

2.2. Factors Affecting On WLB

According to the examined literature, the researcher found a number of factors that have an impact on WLB. In her 2014 essay for the Management Review, Shobitha divided WLB into multiple aspects, including social, organizational, and individual issues. Deep analysis of WLB dimensions can be divided into the following categories:

2.2.1 Individual Factors Which Affecting to Work Life Balance.

Individual factors influencing for WLB has determined in several studies and it has been explained in terms of personality, well-being and emotional intelligence.

- a. **Personality and Work Life Balance.** The Big Five Model, created by McCrae and John, uses five dimensions to explain personality.
- b. **Well-being and WLB.** There are many different facets of health, and psychological health is one of them. It takes into account positive psychology, self-acceptance, satisfaction, hope, or optimism. In light of research findings, it was found that women experience higher levels of well-being than men do, and as a result, they exhibit higher work-life balance in terms of fewer work-family and family-work conflicts. In his research, Wilkinson discovered a favorable relationship between psychological well-being and WLB, and he identified gender as a mediating factor (Wilkinson, 2013).
- c. **Emotional Intelligence.** Affandi and Raza (2000) discovered that emotional intelligence has an effect on the quality of the work life. They also discovered that emotional intelligence is a powerful predictor of WLB and that people with high emotional quotients perform well at work.

2.2.2 Organizational Factors Influencing on WLB

Researchers have discovered the following organizational elements that have an impact on WLB.

- a. **Work Arrangements.** Flexible work schedules may lessen problems between work and personal life, as well as turnover, tardiness, and absenteeism. The study's final finding was that flexible scheduling increases worker productivity. (Christensen, 2010).
- b. **WLB Policies and Programmes.** WLB practices and policies may have an impact on the positive WLB. WLB rules and practices have been highlighted as having potential effects on how women employees grow their careers (Straub, 2017). Addressing problems like gender equality, adaptability, stress management, health knowledge, and childcare may help improve WLB (Rajadhyaksha, 2016).

- c. **Work Support and WLB.** The organization and supervisor support for work-life issues and the decrease of work-family conflict have a beneficial association. (Warner, 2009). Support from coworkers and employment resources that are positively associated to the WLB (Fathima, 2012).
- d. **Job Stress.** Employees who feel uncomfortable or threatened by their jobs may experience job stress. (Stanton, 2001). High levels of workplace stress were found to be positively correlated with increased work family conflict and ill health, but negatively correlated with WLB and wellbeing. WLB and work-life conflict and repercussions (Bell, 2012).

2.2.3 Societal Factors Influencing Work Life Balance

Societal consequences are depicted as follows.

A. **Childcare Responsibilities.** Numerous studies have demonstrated that factors associated to families, such as child care and the number of children, may have a significant impact on WLB. Elliott conducted additional study on the challenges faced by working parents and discovered that those who have young children (under the age of six) are having problems with both their personal and professional lives as a result of insufficient child care. (Elliot, 2015).

B. **Family Support.** Numerous studies have looked into how to manage career and family life with the help of spouses. The family provides adequate practical and emotional support to assist in managing the WLB (Adams, 2011).

2.3. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a reflection of an employee's attitudes regarding their work and how at ease they are in that environment. Job satisfaction is a key factor in consumer behavior, so to satisfy customers, the majority of businesses have introduced training programs and special benefits packages. (Chetnapandey, 2012). All employees in the organization need motivation to increase their performances for that some managers propose to provide more financial benefits to employees while others suggest non-financial benefits. Organizations always make efforts to create satisfied work force because satisfied workers perform well overall productivity of the organization depends on the level of efficiency of employees (Pushpakumari, 2008). (Al-Zoubi, 2012). According to several academics, an employee's happiness is not solely dependent on financial rewards; they also need a pleasant life and needs to be met in a way that makes them happy. Then he came to a conclusion that employee happiness would result from the culmination of all aspects, including financial benefits, a positive work environment, good employee interactions, etc. (BharatiDeshpande, 2012).

3.0. Research Methodology

3.1. Research design

Saunders (2007) says that the research onion model lets researchers figure out their research philosophy by going from the outside to the inside. The onion is important when doing any kind of study.

3.1.1 Research Philosophy

The research philosophy is concerned with the nature of knowledge and how it will be processed. It also contains the researcher's worldview and serves as the foundation for the study plan and methodologies that will be used. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007). The philosophical methodology of the Positivist perspective was used in this study. Factual knowledge is gathered by survey in positivism as a way of research methods. Because the research findings are primarily quantitative and observable, it necessitates an objective methodology.

3.1.2 Research Approach

The deductive technique was utilized since the research approach refers to the use of specific logic or theory to draw conclusions or test hypotheses. Furthermore, it must quantify the link between the factors under consideration, with quantitative data collecting being incorporated. Within the current research study, the

researcher conducted an extensive examination of the literature, and related factors were discovered, as well as a conceptual framework was constructed. The hypotheses were then developed to assess the link between the independent and dependent variables.

3.1.3 Research strategy

According to Saunders et al., (2007), management research employs a variety of research methodologies, including experimental, survey, case study, action research, grounded theory, archival research, and ethnography. This study, on the other hand, will use a survey technique. Surveys are commonly used in business and management research for descriptive and exploratory purposes. Surveys also aid in the collection of massive amounts of data from a large population.

3.2. Data collection

A researcher could perform the research using a qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods study; these research techniques provide specific procedures or direction in a research design. the quantitative method is being applied in this study.

Quantitative research focuses on acquiring numerical data and generalizing it across groups of people. It's also used to explain a certain phenomenon. This project will concentrate on survey research, which emphasizes objective metrics and the mathematical, statistical, or numerical analysis of data acquired via questionnaires and surveys.

Both primary data (using a well-structured questionnaire) and secondary data (using existing sources) were collected.

3.3. Population and Sampling

Asika (2006) defined a population as "all possible subjects, elements, or observations identifying with a specific event of interest to the researcher," whereas Bryman and Bell (2011) defined a population as "a cluster of "units" from which the researcher can select a sample. As such, a sample is a subset of the population that is used for sampling purposes. (Bryman& Bell, 2011).

The study focuses on personnel from 14 different financial organizations in the Ampara area. The study adapts staff assistant / clerk level employees to this research, and around 600 of those employees work in those businesses.

3.3.1 Sampling Technique

The sample population for the study was chosen using a convenience sampling technique from among the 200 employees across 14 financial institutions.

150 questionnaires, or 25% of the population, will be collected from staff assistant and clerk level employees of financial institutions in ampara.

3.4. Analysis Technique

The quantitative data collection method was employed. The quantitative technique was well-structured study questionnaires. The indicators developed under the conceptual framework's independent and dependent variables serve as the foundation for the questionnaire. The first section of the questionnaire contains demographic information and general information on the sample, and the second section has Likert scales. The independent and dependent variables were measured using five-point Likert scales ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

The researcher used descriptive and inferential statistics to examine the acquired data. The researcher used descriptive statistics to conduct frequency analysis for each research issue, and descriptive tables are also given. Correlation and regression analysis are inferential statistical procedures employed here; the results of correlation and regression analysis are provided in tables. SPSS software and Ms-Excel were also employed as data analysis statistical tools.

3.5. Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis Development Relationship between

Many research conducted around the world have found that employment and life happiness are positively associated characteristics (Tait et al., 2013). When there are cultural differences, the likelihood of work family conflicts occurring increases, which can lead to lower levels of job satisfaction and productivity (Anderson et al., 2019). Work-family disputes have also been shown to have an impact on job satisfaction, greater levels of turnover, and tensions. Furthermore, providing training programs as a cure are not much more helpful in increasing job satisfaction through WLB. Clearly, these circumstances imply that employees who are happier in their overall lives are far more likely to be happier at work and report higher levels of job satisfaction. According to studies, the number of hours committed to work has the greatest excess impact on personal contentment levels, with a considerable difference across genders. Unnecessary time allocation for work reduces available time for relaxation and household responsibilities; thus, a balance of home and work life constructs higher levels of job satisfaction. (White et al., 2018).

Nadeem and Abbas (2019) investigated the association between Work Life Conflict and Job contentment and discovered a negative relationship between the variables, implying that supportive management can be a medicine to reduce conflict and increase employee contentment. Malik, Saif, Gomez, Khan, and Hussain (2015) found a positive and substantial association between job satisfaction and work-family balance in another study. According to Anwer and Ikram (2019), job satisfaction is a component of life satisfaction that can occur only if employees can strike a balance between their work and family lives.

Furthermore, they discovered that employees with a high work-life balance are more satisfied with their occupations than individuals with a low work-life balance. As a result; researchers could claim that empirical studies indicate a link between work-life balance and employee happiness.

Figure 1: conceptual framework

The researcher established three hypotheses based on the conceptual framework Developed.

- H1: There is a significant relationship between personal life and job satisfaction of employees in financial institutions in Ampara district.
- H2: There is a significant relationship between organizational factors and job satisfaction of employees in financial institutions in Ampara district.
- H3: There is a significant relationship between social factors and job satisfaction of employees in financial institutions in Ampara district.

4.0. Data Analysis

4.1. Reliability and validity statistics

Table 1: Reliability statistics

Variable	Value
Individual Factors	0.937
Organizational Factors	0.937
Social factors	0.962
Employee satisfaction	0.949

As per the calculated reliability values all variables indicated above 0.7 alpha value therefore it is suitable to go for further analysis.

Table 2: Validity assessment

Variable	KMO Value
Individual Factors	0.801
Organizational Factors	0.728
Social factors	0.794
Employee satisfaction	0.882

According to the validity measurement, all values are more than the 0.5 level. All of the KMO readings exceeded the recommended minimal criterion. As a result, all data was validated.

4.2. Analysis of Sample Profile

The demographic characteristics of the sample, such as age, gender, marital status, and educational credentials, are included, as well as some information about their career. The respondents' service experience at financial institutions. According to their comments, 17% have no to five years of experience, 23% have five to ten years of experience, 40% have 10-15 years of experience, and 20% have 15-20 years of experience. 65% of employees are married, while 35% are unmarried. Sixty percent of married employees' spouses are employed, while forty percent are unemployed. According to the diagram above, 45% of responders are clerk level employees and 55% are staff assistants. According to the above comments, only 35% are content with their jobs, while the bulk of 65% are not.

4.3. Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression is used to determine if the independent factors predict the dependent variable. (criterion). A multiple linear regression model evaluates the connection between a series of dichotomous, ordinal, or interval/ratio predictor variables and an interval/ratio criterion variable. Personal factors and organizational factors are the independent variables in this case, while work satisfaction is the dependent variable. The following regression equation (main effects model) used: $y = b_1 * x_1 + b_2 * x_2 + \dots + c$; where Y = estimated dependent variable, c = constant (which includes the error term), b = regression coefficients and x = each independent variables.

The standard multiple linear regression analysis was employed. The usual method incorporates all independent variables (predictors) into the model at the same time. Unless the theory supports a different way enough, enter is the typical method of variable entering. Variables are assessed based on what they contribute to the prediction of the dependent variable, which differs from the predictability provided by the other predictors in the model. The F-test is used to determine if a set of independent variables predicts the dependent variable collectively. R-squared (the multiple correlation coefficient of determination) is provided and used to estimate how much variance in the dependent variable the set of independent variables can account for. The t test and beta coefficients were used to determine the significance of each predictor and the magnitude of prediction for each independent variable. For significant predictors, the dependent variable will grow or decrease by the number of unstandardized beta coefficients for every unit increase in the predictor.

Multiple regression assumptions such as linearity, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity are evaluated. Linearity posits a straight-line relationship between predictor factors and criterion variables, whereas homoscedasticity assumes that scores are regularly distributed around the regression line. A scatter plot is

used to determine homoscedasticity. The lack of multicollinearity suggests that predictor variables are not overly connected and is evaluated using Variance Inflation Factors. (VIF). VIF values greater than 10 indicate the presence of multicollinearity.

4.3.1 Linearity Test

Table 3: Linearity Test

		Anova ^b				
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	802.982	2	401.491	473.734	.000 ^a
	Residual	11.018	13	.848		
	Total	814.000	15			

A. Predictors: (Constant), organizational, individual, social

B. Dependent Variable: satisfaction

(Source: SPSS analyzed data 2023)

The *F*-ratio in the ANOVA table tests whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The table shows that the independent variables statistically significantly predict the dependent variable because significance level is 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05. I.e., the regression model is a good fit of the data. Furthermore, the test statistic was significant at the .01 level of significance ($F = 473.734$; $p < .01$) as shown in above Table. According to ANOVA table, the value of significance of the

4.3.2 Multicollinearity Test

Table 4: Multicollinearity Test

Model		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Individual factors	.120	8.356
	Organizational factors	.182	5.503
	Social factors	.146	6.827

(Source: SPSS analyzed data 2023)

Multicollinearity test is used to know whether there is correlation or not between independent variables. According to the research findings tolerance is greater than 0.10 and VIF index less than 10 and meets the assumption of multicollinearity. It can define that there is no multicollinearity problem.

4.3.3 Homocedasticity Test

Homocedasticity test is used for identifying whether the variance value of *Y* equal (homogeneous) for each variable *X*. This test is done by looking the Scatter plot, if the data scattered randomly in both *X* and *Y* axis. It means is good because the heterocedasticity problem does not exist.

Table 5: Model summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.993 ^a	.987	.985	.90145

A. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational factors, Personal factors, social factors

(Source: SPSS analyzed data 2023)

The "R" column represents the value of R , the *multiple correlation coefficient*. R can be considered to be one measure of the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable; in this case, employee job satisfaction. A value of 0.993, in this model summary table, indicates a good level of prediction. The "R Square" column represents the R^2 value (also called the coefficient of determination), which is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables (technically, it is the proportion of variation accounted for by the regression model above and beyond the mean model). The above table denotes the r^2 value of 0.987 that the independent variables explain 98.7% of the variability of considered dependent variable job satisfaction. Therefore it is further proven that personal life, social life and organizational life has impact on the employee job satisfaction.

4.4. Correlation Analysis

A correlation study was performed by the researcher to investigate the relationship between independent and dependent variables of individual factors, organizational factors, societal factors, and employee happiness. The hypotheses were developed based on an extensive examination of the literature and conceptual framework to assess the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Thus, connection investigation is used to test the relationship of developed hypotheses on each autonomous and ward aspect independently.

4.4.1 Correlation between personal factors and job satisfaction

H1: There is a significant relationship between personal life and job satisfaction of employees in financial institutions in Ampara district.

Correlation analysis reveals a substantial association between individual variables and job satisfaction in Ampara area banking institutions. Because the correlation between two variables was 0.906. Also, the estimated value is greater than 0.5, indicating that the link between the two variables is strong.

The H1 hypothesis is supported since there is a significant association between individual variables and job satisfaction. Also, because the significance level (p value) is 0.000, the two variables have a significant association and are linearly associated.

4.4.2 Correlation between organizational factors and job satisfaction

H2: There is a significant relationship between organizational factors and job satisfaction of employees in financial institutions in Ampara district.

The above correlation study was carried out in accordance with the researcher's Hypothesis 2. The H_2 hypothesis, which reveals a substantial association between organizational characteristics and work satisfaction with a correlation value of 0.909, was accepted. The association is greater than 0.5, indicating that the relationship between the two variables is very strong and significant.

4.4.3 Correlation between social factors and employee performance

H3: There is a significant relationship between social factors and job satisfaction of employees in financial institutions in Ampara district.

The researcher attempted to determine whether there is a substantial relationship between social characteristics and job satisfaction in financial institutions in the Ampara district. Several questions were asked of the respondents to ensure the impact of the social component, which included several aspects. According to the correlation value of 0.994, there is a considerable association between social dimension and job satisfaction, and the two variables are linearly associated.

5.0. Findings and conclusions

5.1 Overall summary of the study

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of WLB on employee job satisfaction in Ampara area banking institutions. The primary goal of the research was to identify signs of decreasing work satisfaction among employees in financial organizations. As a result, the researcher sought to study the rationale for the fact and wanted to conduct additional research on WLB and job satisfaction. The researcher

conducted a thorough analysis of the literature to describe past studies and key hypotheses connected to WLB and job satisfaction. Following a review of the literature, the researcher developed a conceptual framework indicating the study's independent and dependent variables. Three independent variables were identified as individual factors, social factors, and organizational factors, with job satisfaction being the dependent variable. Based on the independent and dependent variables depicted on the conceptual framework, hypotheses were formed.

The researcher obtained both primary and secondary data for the research investigation. The information was gathered from the selected sample via a survey investigation. The survey was carried out using a structured self-administered questionnaire distributed to 70 employees of financial institutions in the Ampara district. Data were evaluated statistically using SPSS software including both inferential and descriptive statistics. All of the questions in the research questionnaire were subjected to frequency analysis. Pearson correlation analysis was used to examine other hypotheses. All hypotheses were accepted based on the correlation analysis that was performed.

5.2 Conclusion

According to the findings of the research study, employees in financial institutions in the Ampara district are dissatisfied with their jobs because they are unhappy with their professional and personal lives. They would be unable to balance their personal and professional lives while working. Aside from that, they face a number of challenges from an individual, organizational, and social standpoint. With these characteristics, researchers can assume that employees are dissatisfied as a result of the numerous difficulties they face. As a result, researchers can conclude that people lack the ability to obtain higher levels of job satisfaction and that their job front is influenced by individual, organizational, and social factors.

The overall conclusion of the research study is that WLB has a significant impact on the job satisfaction of employees in financial institutions in the Ampara district. Individual characteristics, social factors, and organizational aspects are used to calculate WLB. After analyzing primary data, the researcher discovered that the majority of employees are dissatisfied with their jobs. All personal, societal, and organizational aspects have a significant impact on gaining job satisfaction.

6.0. Limitations and Areas for Future Researchers

This research study is carried out with the limited time frame and researcher could not be able to capture all financial institutions in Sri Lanka. If researcher would be able to target more respondents findings would be more reliable. As per the convenience of the data collection, researcher gathered data only from financial institutions located within Ampara district and captured only 70 respondents. The future researchers are recommended to increase the sample size as well as capture the all financial institutions in Sri Lanka not limiting to single geographical area.

Subsequently this thesis can be carried out for different industries. So the future researchers can conduct research studies in different industries. Due to the prevailing worse pandemic of Covid-19, researcher selected only one data collection mode i.e. Research questionnaire. If the researcher would be able to use more data collection techniques, the results would be more reliable.

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